

Space charge influence on particles channeling in optical lattice

S.B. Dabagov^{a,b,c,*}, E.N. Frolov^b, A.V. Dik^b

^a INFN Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati, Frascati, Italy

^b RAS P.N. Lebedev Physical Institute, Moscow, Russia

^c NR Nuclear University MEPhI, Moscow, Russia

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the effect of a space charge on the dynamics of relativistic particles in a laser channel has been considered. We derived the expression for effective potential describing the dynamics of charged particles including into the study the interaction of particles with each other. Analysing general concepts on the distribution of a particle beam in a channel, we have formulated the condition, which determines the limits of applicability of the perturbation theory when space charge is taken into account.

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1. Introduction

Charged particle interaction with nonuniform electromagnetic waves has been drawing increasing attention since the pioneering publication on electron scattering in the field of standing waves [1]. Later, with the availability of new radiation sources with continuously increasing photon flux intensities, research groups have obtained new tools to study the interaction of particles in various fields. In particular, lasers now offer unprecedented level of coherency, monochromaticity and power suitable to form “effective optical lattices”. The latter might be described as an electromagnetic counterpart of a crystal lattice since both are capable of trapping charged particles in a channeling regime.

The first article addressing channeling in laser field, implicitly introducing critical channeling angle for the process [2], has proposed the classical electron dynamics in crossed laser beams (common example of the optical lattice) [3–8]. The most thorough description of classical charged particle dynamics in nonuniform laser field is given in [9]. Effective potential describing the dynamics in a field of two arbitrary aligned lasers of various polarisations

has been defined for a classical particle [8] as well as for a spinless quantum particle [10].

Channeling of charged particles in optical lattice is closely connected to the Kapitza–Dirac effect [11]. Based on the Kapitza analytical method, the phenomenon for non-relativistic quantum particles is described in [12], while its extension for a particle with the spin – in [13–15].

All aforementioned works are devoted to the dynamics of a single particle, since studying the space charge effect is a challenging task even within the simplest approximation. Numerical simulation is usually used to address the problem of internal charged particle beam forces. Such simulation for charged particles in optical lattice has been already carried out [16]. However, the drawback of the numerical analysis is the inherent lack of generality. At the same time, the role of research taking a space charge into account is increasing. That is not only because it provides information on a threshold beam density to be confined in laser channels [17] but also because effective potential channels are formed by the external high-frequency field. And in case of many charged particles trapped in a channel, if the beam charge is dense enough, the emitted radiation (oscillating electromagnetic field) may interfere with the external field distorting the averaged channeling potential.

* Corresponding author at: INFN Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati, Frascati, Italy.

E-mail address: sultan.dabagov@lnf.infn.it (S.B. Dabagov).

Below, based on the quantum formalism, we present our latest results on the space charge effect for charged particles channeling in an optical lattice.

2. The equation of motion

Let us consider a system of interacting spinless charged particles moving in a nonuniform laser field of the frequency ω_0 and 4-potential $A^\mu = (0, \mathbf{A}_l)$. Charged particle oscillations in the nonuniform laser field \mathbf{A}_l might be integrated into averaged channeling oscillations, which can be described by an effective interaction potential [8]. Assuming the number of particles to be constant, each of them (denominated by j) is described by a wave function Ψ_j . Therefore, the entire Lagrangian system can be presented as follows [18]

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(\mathcal{L}_f^j + \mathcal{L}_{int}^j \right) + \mathcal{L}_e, \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{L}_f^j is the j -th free spinless particle Lagrangian, \mathcal{L}_{int}^j is the Lagrangian, which describes its interaction with the external field and other particles, \mathcal{L}_e is the electromagnetic field Lagrangian. Therefore, the Lagrange equation for dynamics of a spinless quantum particle of charge e and mass m can be written as

$$\sum_{k \neq j} \left[\left(i\hbar \partial_\mu + \frac{e}{c} (A_\mu + A_\mu^k) \right) \times \left(i\hbar \partial^\mu + \frac{e}{c} (A^\mu + A^\mu_k) \right) - m^2 c^2 \right] \Psi^j = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\partial_\nu \partial^\nu A_\mu^k = -\frac{2\pi e}{mc} \Psi_k \left(i\hbar \partial_\mu - \frac{e}{c} \sum_{j \neq k} A_\mu^j \right) \Psi_k^* + c.c., \quad (3)$$

where A_μ^k is the 4-potential for the field of k -th particle and ∂_μ is the 4-gradient. The expression (2) describes the motion in the total field formed by the laser A_μ and other particles $A_{int}^\mu = (\varphi_i, \mathbf{A}_i)$. Now, based on previous results [10], let us derive the potential describing the particles interaction.

Assuming that the energies of particle interaction with the laser field and the other particles are both much less than the particle longitudinal motion energy $\hbar\omega_\parallel$, where the particle longitudinal momentum is $p_\parallel = \hbar q_z$, the solution of the equation (2) can be written in the form (we omit the particle index for brevity):

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \bar{\psi}_{q_z}(\mathbf{r}, t) \chi(\mathbf{r}, t) e^{i(q_z z - \omega_\parallel t)} \quad (4)$$

According to the Kapitza method, the function $\bar{\psi}_{q_z}$ describes the smooth channeled motion of a particle and χ – the oscillations in a fast periodic field with frequency $\omega = \omega_0 - \beta_\parallel c k_z^0$. Here ω_0 is the laser field frequency, k_z^0 is the wave vector projection for a nonuniform laser wave onto the Oz axis (along the channel axis), $\beta_\parallel = q_z c / \omega_\parallel$ is the particle longitudinal velocity, $\hbar\omega_\parallel = \sqrt{(\hbar q_z)^2 + (mc)^2}$ is the longitudinal energy of the particle. As a result, for the functions $\bar{\psi}_{q_z}$ and χ we obtain equations similar to those presented in [10]

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial t} = \left(e\beta_\parallel A_l^z - \frac{i\hbar e \mathbf{A}_l \nabla \ln \bar{\psi}_{q_z}}{\gamma_\parallel mc} + \frac{e^2 A_l^2}{2\gamma_\parallel mc^2} \right) \chi \quad (5)$$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \bar{\psi}_{q_z}}{\partial t} = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2\gamma_\parallel m} \nabla^2 + U_{eff} + \bar{V} \right) \bar{\psi}_{q_z}, \quad (6)$$

where U_{eff} is the effective potential describing the interaction of a particle with the laser field, A_l^2 is the periodic in time part of the

squared external laser field A_l^2 , \bar{V} is the operator responsible for the interaction with other particles

$$\bar{V} = -\frac{i\hbar ec}{\hbar\omega_\parallel} \bar{\mathbf{A}}_i \nabla + e\beta_\parallel \bar{A}_i^z - \frac{i\hbar e \bar{\varphi}_i}{\hbar\omega_\parallel} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \beta_\parallel c \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \right) + \frac{e^2 (\bar{A}_i^2 - \bar{\varphi}_i^2)}{2\hbar\omega_\parallel} - e\bar{\varphi}_i \quad (7)$$

The bar over the field potentials means averaging. Since we consider the particle interaction energy to be much less than its longitudinal energy, the interaction operator can be written as

$$\bar{V} = e\beta_\parallel \bar{A}_i^z - e\bar{\varphi}_i, \quad (8)$$

with the averaged potentials describing the interaction among particles defined by the expressions

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \bar{A}_i^z = 4\pi \frac{e\hbar q_z}{mc} \sum_{k \neq j} \left| \bar{\psi}_{q_z}^k \right|^2 \quad (9)$$

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) \bar{\varphi}_i = 4\pi \frac{e\hbar\omega_\parallel}{mc^2} \sum_{k \neq j} \left| \bar{\psi}_{q_z}^k \right|^2 \quad (10)$$

The right-hand sides of Eqs. (9), (10) can be rewritten in the form

$$\sum_k \left| \bar{\psi}_k \right|^2 = \frac{1}{\gamma_\parallel} \sum_k \rho_k = \frac{1}{\gamma_\parallel} F(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (11)$$

where ρ_k is the probability density distribution of the k -th particle, and the longitudinal Lorentz factor $\gamma_\parallel = \hbar\omega_\parallel / mc^2$ appears due to the wave functions normalization for the Klein–Gordon–Fock equation. Thus, we obtain a system of equations for N particles that must be solved. In this paper we are not seeking for the exact solution of relativistic particles beam dynamics in a laser channel, but confine ourselves to the intensity of the effect for space charge on particle dynamics. To this purpose we denote the particle distribution function in a channel as $F(\mathbf{r}, t)$. Then the interaction operator of relativistic particles takes the form

$$\bar{V} = -\frac{e}{\gamma_\parallel^2} \bar{\varphi}_i \quad (12)$$

with the scalar potential

$$\bar{\varphi}_i(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\int_V \frac{e}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} F(\mathbf{r}', t - \frac{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}{c}) d^3 r' \quad (13)$$

As stated above our main goal is to describe how both beam size and number of particles may affect the beam dynamics.

3. Space charge influence on particle dynamics

For sake of simplicity let us consider an infinite particle beam in the directions Y, Z , and the one-dimensional problem corresponding to planar channeling. We limit our analysis to the parabolic potential, in which the potential energy is defined by (see in [10])

$$U_{eff}(x) = \frac{\gamma_\parallel m \Omega_0^2(\beta_\parallel)}{2} x^2, \quad (14)$$

where $\Omega_0(\beta_\parallel)$ is the frequency of a channeling motion that depends on the particle longitudinal velocity. The distribution function for particles in the channel is chosen in the form of a Gaussian distribution

$$F(x) = \frac{N_0}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad (15)$$

Fig. 1. The effective potential for the interaction of a beam of charged particles with a laser field as well as with others near the bottom of the channel where the effective potential is represented by the parabola.

where N_0 is the particle density per unit surface, and σ is the characteristic transverse dimension of the beam. The field corresponding to such distribution with additional conditions of zero field at zero point and of symmetry with respect to the coordinate sign is given as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\varphi}_i(x) = & 2\pi e N_0 \left[\operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right) x + \right. \\ & \left. + \sigma \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \left(e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}} - 1 \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The effective potential describing the interaction of particles with the laser and particles among themselves is shown in Fig. 1. In this case, no exact analytical solution could be obtained except the semiclassical approximation that is valid at the bottom of the well where the approximation of parabolic potential does not work. However, if we assume a small perturbation, corrections to the energy levels for the n -th energy level can be calculated by the expression

$$\delta E_n = -\frac{2\pi e^2 N_0 \sigma}{\gamma_{\parallel}^2} F_n \left(\frac{\sigma}{\lambda} \right) \quad (17)$$

Here $1/\lambda = \sqrt{\gamma_{\parallel} m \Omega_0 / \hbar}$ defines the minimum characteristic size of the particle localisation region, and the dimensionless function $F_n(\xi)$ is expressed in terms of hypergeometric functions series and, as seen in Eq. (17), the energy correction depends on the beam size. The function $F_n(\xi)$ is maximal for $\xi = 1$ and decreases monotonously at the argument increase. In the limit of large ξ the correction to the energy becomes

$$\delta E_n \approx -\frac{\sqrt{2\pi} e^2 N_0 \lambda}{\gamma_{\parallel}^2} \frac{\lambda}{\sigma} \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (18)$$

In Fig. 2 the dependence of F_n for several levels n on the ratio σ/λ is presented. The above results indicate that at constant parameters, the greatest absolute value of the energy correction corresponds to the beam of minimum width $\sigma = \lambda$. Introducing the value $U_0 = \pi e^2 N_0 \sigma / \gamma_{\parallel}^2$, the ratio of the energy correction to the energy itself can be presented by the following

$$\left| \frac{\delta E_n}{E_n} \right| = \frac{U_0}{\hbar \Omega_0} \frac{2 F_n(1)}{2n+1} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 2. Dependence of the dimensionless function $F(\xi)$ on the dimensionless characteristic size of the beam $\xi = \sigma/\lambda$ for 4 various quantum states $n = 0, 1, 5, 10$.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the dimensionless energy correction on the energy itself for the densest beam as a function of the quantum level number. As seen this feature becomes important for low-lying levels.

The absolute dimensionless value of the ratio of the energy to its correction as a function of the level number is shown in Fig. 3. Analysing the figure we can conclude that the corrections are not insignificant for the lower levels. Thus, the interaction of particles between them can be considered as a small perturbation if the following condition is satisfied

$$\Omega_0(\beta_{\parallel}) \gg \frac{\omega_p}{\gamma_{\parallel}^{3/2}}, \quad (20)$$

where $\omega_p = (4\pi e^2 n_0 / m)^{1/2}$ is the plasma frequency. The factor $\gamma_{\parallel}^{3/2}$ in the expression can be explained by the Doppler effect, in other words, is the “weight” of a particle $m \rightarrow \gamma_{\parallel} m$. Thus, from Eq. (20) one can obtain the following threshold for the electron/positron beam density

$$n_0 = \frac{N_0}{\sigma} \ll 4 \cdot 10^3 I \gamma_{\parallel}, \quad (21)$$

where n_0 is the concentration in cm^{-3} , and I is the intensity of the laser field in W/cm^2 . For example, for an electron beam with a longitudinal Lorentz factor $\gamma_{\parallel} = 10^3$, channeled in a microwave laser field of the intensity $I = 10^{16} \text{ W/cm}^2$, the interaction might be regarded as a perturbation, if the beam density satisfies the inequality $n_0 \ll 4 \cdot 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Moreover, for a 1 cm beam with 10 μm transverse size, it gives a restriction for the charge of $Q \ll 10^4 \text{ nC}$. It should be underlined that the typical charge may be 1 nC. From this analysis it can be concluded that for existing electron/positron beams of energy $\gamma_{\parallel} \geq 10^3$ and with laser fields

of intensity $I \geq 10^{16}$ W/cm², the charge will not affect the channeling characteristics. Thus, laser channels can be used in collision processes of both singly charged particle beams ($e^\pm + e^\pm$) and with different charges ($e^+ + e^-$).

4. Conclusions

When particle interaction with external laser field is stronger than particle-particle interactions, the latter can be described using averaged 4-potentials. In particular, the scalar component of the 4-potential over the inverse longitudinal energy squared might be used as a first approximation of the interaction operation expansion.

In this work the influence of the space charge effect on charged particle beam dynamics at laser planar channeling has been estimated for the general case of a Gaussian beam distribution revealing the inverse proportionality to the beam size (Eq. (17) and Fig. 2). This phenomenon reaches its maximum for lower level particles and is essentially weaker for particles with higher energies (Eq. (19) and Fig. 3).

Notably, particle-particle interaction is faint at certain conditions (see, for instance, Eq. (21)) and does not substantially affect the beam dynamics. For relativistic and ultrarelativistic electrons/positrons ($\gamma_{||} \geq 10^3$) in an optical lattice of $I \geq 10^{16}$ W/cm² the space charge impact to the beam dynamics is negligible. Hence, the optical lattice might be a promising tool for future beam colliding facilities allowing beams shaping, collimation and guiding.

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